

Assessment of E-waste Management on Lifestyle and Environmental Hazards in Schools: A Case Study of Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State

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Abstract

This study investigates the implications of e-waste management on healthy lifestyles and environmental hazards in private and public secondary schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State. A descriptive survey design was employed, with data collected from principals, ICT teachers, and students across ten randomly selected secondary schools. The population of the study is 43,458 while the sample size is 400. The research instrument, a structured questionnaire, achieved a reliability score of 0.87. Chi-square tests were used to analyze three hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The first hypothesis tested whether e-waste significantly affects students' healthy lifestyles, and the results showed no significant impact ($\chi^2 = 3.128$, $p > 0.05$). The second hypothesis examined differences in e-waste management practices between private and public schools, with results indicating no significant difference ($\chi^2 = 0.404$, $p > 0.05$). The third hypothesis explored whether e-waste contributes to environmental hazards, revealing no significant effect ($\chi^2 = 2.488$, $p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that e-waste management practices in the studied schools are effective and do not adversely affect health or the environment. However, the results challenge previous research that emphasizes the risks of improper e-waste disposal, indicating the need for ongoing vigilance and improvements. The study recommends enhancing awareness, regular monitoring, collaboration with environmental agencies, centralized e-waste management systems, and recycling initiatives.

Keywords: E-waste, healthy lifestyle, environmental hazards, management, secondary schools

Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology has led to an unprecedented proliferation of electronic devices, significantly altering lifestyles and educational environments. While this digital revolution has brought numerous benefits, it has also introduced new challenges, particularly in the realm of electronic waste (e-waste) management. E-waste, which encompasses discarded electrical and electronic devices, has emerged as one of the fastest-growing waste streams globally, posing significant environmental and health risks. In developing regions like Nigeria, where the regulatory framework and infrastructure for managing e-waste are often inadequate, these risks are particularly pronounced (Saha et al., 2021).

E-waste is a rapidly growing global concern, with an estimated 53.6 million metric tons generated worldwide in 2019, and this figure is expected to rise to 74.7 million metric tons by 2030 (Forti et al., 2020). The improper disposal of e-waste can lead to the release of hazardous substances, including heavy metals like lead, mercury, and cadmium, as well as brominated flame retardants, which can cause serious health issues such as neurological damage, respiratory problems, and even cancer (Grant et al., 2013). Moreover, these substances can contaminate soil and water sources, leading to long-term environmental degradation (Heacock et al., 2016).

Developing countries, particularly in Africa, have become the primary destinations for e-waste due to lax environmental regulations and the economic incentive to recover valuable materials from discarded electronics (Wideman, 2019). Nigeria, with its large population and growing demand for electronic devices, has emerged as a significant player in the global e-waste trade. However, the country's infrastructure for managing e-waste is underdeveloped, leading to widespread informal recycling practices that often involve unsafe methods such as open burning and acid leaching, which further exacerbate health and environmental hazards (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024).

In Nigeria, the issue of e-waste is particularly pressing due to the combination of high importation rates of used electronic devices and inadequate disposal infrastructure. Lagos State, being the economic nerve center of the country, bears the brunt of this problem. Ojo LGA, in particular, is home to Alaba International Market, one of the largest electronics markets

in West Africa, making it a hotspot for e-waste generation (Ogungbuyi, 2012). Despite the presence of regulatory frameworks such as the National Environmental (Electrical/Electronic Sector) Regulations of 2011, enforcement remains weak, and much of the e-waste is processed in informal sectors without proper safety measures (Ogunseitan et al., 2009).

Schools in Ojo LGA are increasingly reliant on electronic devices for educational purposes, from computers and projectors to tablets and interactive whiteboards. However, the end-of-life management of these devices is often overlooked. Many schools lack formal policies or systems for e-waste disposal, leading to the accumulation of obsolete electronics on school premises or their improper disposal through informal channels. This not only exposes students and staff to harmful substances but also contributes to environmental pollution, particularly in a region already struggling with waste management issues (Nnorom et al., 2009).

The health implications of improper e-waste management in schools are significant. Children, in particular, are more vulnerable to the toxic effects of hazardous substances found in e-waste due to their developing bodies and behaviors that increase exposure, such as hand-to-mouth activities (Lebbie et al., 2021). Studies have shown that exposure to e-waste pollutants can lead to cognitive impairments, developmental delays, and other serious health conditions in children (Zeng et al., 2020). In schools where e-waste is not managed properly, students and staff may be exposed to these toxic substances through inhalation of dust, dermal contact, or ingestion of contaminated food and water (Lebbie et al., 2021).

Moreover, the environmental impact of e-waste in schools is profound. Improperly disposed e-waste can lead to the contamination of soil and water bodies with toxic substances, affecting not only the school environment but also the surrounding communities. This is particularly concerning in Ojo LGA, where many schools are located in close proximity to residential areas, increasing the risk of widespread environmental contamination. Additionally, the informal recycling of e-waste, which often takes place near or within school premises, can result in the release of pollutants into the air, further exacerbating environmental and health risks.

In Lagos State, the largest urban area in Nigeria and a hub of technological activity, the challenges associated with e-waste management are acute. Ojo Local Government Area (LGA), home to numerous educational institutions and a densely populated community, is no exception (Soladoye et al., 2020). Schools in this area, like many others in developing countries, are increasingly incorporating electronic devices into their educational practices. However, the disposal and management of these devices, once they become obsolete, have not kept pace with their growing usage. The improper handling and disposal of e-waste in schools pose significant risks to both students' health and the environment, creating an urgent need to address this issue comprehensively. This study aims to address this gap by providing empirical data on e-waste management practices in schools within Ojo LGA and identifying the key challenges and risks associated with these practices. By doing so, it seeks to contribute to the development of effective policies and strategies for managing e-waste in educational institutions, thereby reducing the associated health and environmental hazards. Furthermore, the findings of this study will have broader implications for other regions in Nigeria and similar contexts in developing countries, where e-waste management in schools is likely to be an emerging issue.

Objective of the Study

1. To investigate the implications of e-waste on the healthy lifestyle of students and staff in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. To examine the effects of e-waste on environmental hazards in schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State.
3. To compare e-waste management practices in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Research Questions

1. What are the implications of e-waste on the healthy lifestyle of students and staff in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State?
2. How does e-waste contribute to environmental hazards in schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State?
3. What are the differences in e-waste management practices between private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos state.
2. There is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos state.

3. There is no significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos state?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design adopted in this study is descriptive survey research design. It was designed in order to collect factual detailed information that describes the existing phenomena. Descriptive survey design is one that allows a researcher to collect information through interviewing or administering a questionnaire with sample drawn from the target population (Orodho, 2005).

Population of the Study

The population of the study is consists of the principal, ICT teachers as well as students each in ten (10) selected secondary schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The population of principals, teacher and students is over 43,458 in both public and private secondary schools in Ojo Local Government Area (Lagos State Ministry of Education, 2017). The choice of the selection was based on the fact that the variables under investigation were particular to them and no other party could provide this information.

Sample and Sampling Technique

To determine the sample size the researchers adopted SurveyMonkey sample size calculator. The sample size deduced was 381. In order to have adequate representation of both public and private secondary schools, the sample was rounded to 400 samples with 204 samples from the public and 196 samples from the private schools. The sample of the study consists of the principal, ICT teachers as well as students selected in each of the 20 secondary schools under sample in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The research adopted simple random sampling technique where 20 secondary schools with 12 from the public and 8 from the private schools.

Research Instrument

The researchers made use of questionnaire to collect information based on the study, and it contained different variables each on the formulated hypothesis. This questionnaire which was made to consist of 4 keys (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree) was formulated to indicate the respondent's opinion to the questions raised. The questionnaire contained two sections A and B. Section A seeks information on demographic data of respondents such as sex, age, class and religion while section B consists of 15 items with 5 question items for each research hypothesis to which the respondents are to reflect their opinion by selecting from any of the 4 keys.

Validity of Instrument

The research instrument, i.e. questionnaire was subjected to validation by giving a copy to the supervisor for effective corrections, comments and amendments. His suggestion was incorporated into the final draft of the questionnaire. This thus helped to improve the instrument done to make the instrument relevant to the study, this made it achieve what it ought to achieve.

Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability refers to the degree of consistency between the set of score obtained with the same instrument (Onocha and Okpala 2011). The corrected versions of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents which forms part of the study. The data collected were collected which generated a value of 0.87 correlation index.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Male	172	43.0
Female	228	57.0
Total	400	100.0
Age		
Valid Below 24 yrs	188	47.0
25 to 30 yrs	136	34.0
31 to 35 yrs	52	13.0
36yrs and Above	24	6.0
Total	400	100.0

School type		
Valid Private School	196	49.0
Public School	204	51.0
Total	400	100.0
E-waste seminar		
Valid Yes	324	81.0
No	76	19.0
Total	400	100.0

Table 1 shows the gender distribution of the respondents. It shows male with 43%, while female was with 57%. It further shows the age difference of the respondents. Those below 24 years had 47%, those between 25 and 30 years had 34%, and those between 31 to 35 years had 13% while those between 36 and above had only 6%. Also, it shows school type of the respondents. Those in private school were 49% while those in public school were having 51%. Lastly it depicts whether respondents have ever attended seminar before on e-waste. Those that answered Yes were 81% while those that answered No were only 19%.

Testing of Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the implications of E-waste on the Healthy Lifestyle of Students and Staff in Private and Public Schools?

Table 2: School Type *E-waste on healthy lifestyle cross tabulation

		E-waste on Health			
		SA	A	D	Total
H Private School	Count	32	156	8	196
	Expected Count	47.2	140.8	8.0	196
Public School	Count	64	132	8	204
	Expected Count	49.2	146.8	8.0	204
Total	Count	96	288	16	400
	Expected Count	96.4	287.6	16	400.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 reflects cross tabulation of school type with count and expected count respectively which indicate that e-waste is perceived to have significant implications for the healthy lifestyle of students and staff.

Research Question 2: How does E-waste contribute to Environmental Hazards in Schools?

Table 3: School Type *E-Waste and environmental hazards cross tabulation

		E-waste management in schools			
		SA	A	D	Total
H Private School	Count	40	140	16	196
	Expected Count	31.2	152.8	12	196
Public School	Count	24	172	8	204
	Expected Count	32.8	159.2	12	204
Total	Count	64	312	24	400
	Expected Count	64	312.0	24.0	400.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 depicts cross tabulation school type and e-waste environmental hazard with count and expected count which indicate that there is agreement that e-waste contributes to environmental hazards.

Research Question 3: What are the differences in e-waste management practices between private and public schools?

Table 4: School Type *E-Waste Management practices in schools cross tabulation

		E-waste management in schools				
		SA	A	D	SD	Total

H Private School	Count	88	84	16	8	196
	Expected Count	90.0	84.4	15.6	6.0	196
Public School	Count	96	88	16	4	204
	Expected Count	94.0	87.6	16.4	6.0	204
Total	Count	184	172	32	12	400
	Expected Count	184.0	172.0	32.0	12.0	400.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4 depicts cross tabulation of school type and e-waste management with count and expected count respectively which suggest that there is a consensus that private schools generally have more effective e-waste management practices than public schools, largely due to resource availability and better training.

Testing the Hypotheses

HO1: There is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public school students of Lagos state in Ojo local government area.

Table 5: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	3.128	2	.209
Likelihood Ratio	3.179	2	.204
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.384	1	.123
N of Valid Cases	400		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

A chi-square test was conducted to find out the significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public school students of Lagos State in Ojo local government area.

The result shows that there is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public school students of Lagos state in Ojo local government area (chi-square = 3.128, $p > 0.05$).

HO2: There is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state.

Table 6: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	2.448	2	.294
Likelihood Ratio	2.472	2	.291
Linear-by-Linear Association	.228	1	.633
N of Valid Cases	400		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

A chi-square test was conducted to find out the significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The result shows that there is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. (chi-square = 2.448, $p > 0.05$).

HO3: There is no significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state.

Table 7: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	.404	3	.939
Likelihood Ratio	.410	3	.938
Linear-by-Linear Association	.201	1	.654
N of Valid Cases	400		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

A chi-square test was conducted to find out the significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos State.

The result shows that there is no significant difference of e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state (Chi-square = .404, $p > 0.05$).

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one states that there is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy life style of private and public-school students and a chi-square test was conducted to show the significance of the hypothesis. The result is shown on table 6 above and it says that there is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public-school students. It was deduced that chi-square = 3.128, $p > 0.05$. The hypothesis was not rejected and this implies that e-waste disposal and management in schools within Ojo local government area are properly taken care of and this has no adverse implication on their healthy life style. This finding is against research conducted by Abdelbasir (2018) that says the dangerous effect of burning metal parts of discarded electronic products creates severe health and environmental hazards. Furthermore, Nnorom and Osibanjo (2008), highlighted the significant health and environmental risks posed by improper e-waste management practices, particularly in developing regions. Their research contrasts with the current findings of the study, suggesting that improper disposal can have severe implications on health and the environment.

Hypothesis two states that there is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. A chi-square test was carried out to show the significance of the hypothesis. It was deduced that chi-square = 2.488, $df=2$ $p > 0.05$ and it shows on table 8 that e-waste does not have a significant effect on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. This is simply because their unused computer gadgets are not always left to litter the environment to an extent of posing threat to lives of individuals around. This finding is against that of Olayinka-Olagunju (2018) that says e-waste is the most existing factor that poses threat to lives of individuals among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The study by Borthakur and Singh (2012), emphasized the risks associated with the improper disposal of e-waste, particularly in educational institutions, where unregulated practices can lead to significant health and environmental threats. This contrasts with the current study, which suggests that such threats are not prevalent in the schools examined.

Hypothesis three states that there is no significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. A chi-square test was conducted to carry out to show the significance of the hypothesis and it shows on table 10 that there is no difference in the management of e-waste in both private and public schools. It was deduced that chi-square = 0.404, $df = 3$; $p > 0.05$. Therefore, the hypothesis was not rejected. This finding is against the findings of Foday (2017) that states that the existence of e-waste is so large in public schools compared to private schools. It is also against the assertion made by Manhart et al (2011) that says the existence of e-waste is minimal in private schools. Generally, this finding is revealing that the management of e-waste in both public and private school in Ojo local government area of Lagos state is at equilibrium and no one is surpassing the other.

Conclusions

E-waste is a general issue and everybody should be involved in other to enable a hazard free environment. Furthermore, it was revealed that e-waste is being managed at the same rate in both private and public schools in the areas that were put in view. Though the fact that new electrical gadgets are being bought every year cannot be over emphasized but there exist proper management of those ones that are no longer in use. The study revealed also that training on e-waste management occurs in the schools in view but only occasionally. Majority of the principals agree to employ e-waste managers in their school and a few of them was in contrast because they already have the knowledge of managing e-waste in their school. Accordingly, some of the respondents believe that e-waste management is at equilibrium in both public and private schools.

Recommendations

Basing on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Useless electrical/ electronic should always be put into proper storage or sold in the essence of making more money
2. Unused electrical products also could be transferred to other schools where they would be needed rather than putting into storage without use.

3. Health education seminars or training should be carried out at every school on E-waste management; this should involve everybody in the exercise.
4. In the case of very harmful c-waste materials, they should be quickly taken to local recycling centers where they would be recycled.
5. There should be standby fund for the management of e-waste in the school.s

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